

A STUDY OF SOCIAL INTELLIGENCE OF COLLEGE STUDENTS

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Introduction :

In modern age of civilization, we are living in a world of different type of social and personal conditions. But human behaviour is regulated in both social and personal fields by his "Sociality." Sociality can restrict his behaviour and activities. He can perform better in every situation and place of work, by proper control on his sociality.

Living in a society in which special skills in particular social abilities are needed to build and maintain the community, humans had to evolve specific competencies to allow them to survive and reproduce. As the society became more complex. The intellectual competencies became more sophisticated. This emerging competence is social intelligence and can be defined as the intelligence that lies behind group interactions and behaviours. This type of intelligence is closely related to but different from cognition and emotional intelligence.

As far as our nation India is concerned it is totally a customized country, and every citizen of our country is totally bounded in a well civilized and traditional society. In this regard, the term Social Intelligence is very much useful in our society. But the term Social Intelligence is in an infant stage in our nation, other concepts related to intelligence such as emotional intelligence, academic intelligence and any other is a well known term used in all the books and in various other researches and publications. But the concept of social intelligence is relatively new concept for our Indian society.

In the world scenario psychologists are using the concept of Social Intelligence in world class business and professions and they witness its effect. In this background, the investigator became interested and curious in the dimension of intelligence.

Need of the Study :

Social Intelligence has much to do with knowing when and how to express sociality as it does with controlling it. Instance consider popular science writer Daniel Goleman has drawn on social neuroscience and Paul Ekman has created the Micro Expression Training Tool, to allow people to practice identifying the brief emotional expressions that flit across peoples faces. The website Mind Habits.com offers a research based software program with which people learn to modify mind habits attention to the social threats and rejections that can cause stress Other interventions for example to help autistic individuals develop social perception and interaction skills, are also in development.

As everyone knows that education is major tool is for the social change and Social Intelligence related to teachers and students, it gives a major milestone performance in the teaching-learning process administration, curriculum construction and basically in the interaction between teachers and students.

Keeping in view the importance of Social intelligence in every aspect of human behaviour it's study is very important. When the student go through the Social process of education, they develop some sort of Social intelligence. When these students are at the stage oh higher education, they have already some amount of Social intelligence due to their personal life experiences and previous education. At this stage, if necessary, some intervention may be carried out in order to make them successful in their future life. The investigator felt compelled to study Social intelligence among college students.

Statement of the Problem :

The problem for the present study has been entitled as "A Study of Social intelligence of College students".

Operational Definitions :

Social - Constituted to live in society, having developed or fulfilled tendencies to organize in society as a race or people. (Webster's Comprehensive Dictionary, Trident Press International, Columbia U.S.A.2003,p.p.-1191)

Intelligence - Wagnon (1937) stated, "Intelligence is the capacity to learn and adjust to relatively new and changing conditions".

Social Intelligence - To respond expertly to the problems of social life, it is necessary to be well endowed with Social Intelligence. As intellectual problem solving, social problem solving requires knowledge strategies and plan. Social knowledge includes information about people and situations, strategies and plans include the ways in which intentions are translated into a series of action.

Student - A person engaged in a course of study especially one in a secondary school college or college.

Objectives of the study :

- ❖ To compare Social Intelligence between male and female students of professional courses in I.P. P.G. College, Bulandshahr, U.P.
- ❖ To compare Social Intelligence between rural and urban students of various professional courses in I.P. P.G. College, Bulandshahr, U.P.
- ❖ To compare Social Intelligence between students of various faculties of the I.P. P.G. College, Bulandshahr, U.P.

Hypotheses

- ❖ There is no significant difference between male and female students on various dimensions of social intelligence.
- ❖ There is no significant difference between rural and urban students on various dimensions of Social Intelligence.
- ❖ There is no significant difference between students of three faculties- Faculty of Education, Faculty of Bio-Technology and Faculty of Computer Science on various dimension of Social Intelligence.

Delimitation of Study :

- ❖ Study is delimited to students of professional courses in three main faculties - Faculty of Education, Faculty of Bio-Technology and Faculty of Computer Science in I.P.P.G. College, Bulandshahr, U.P..

- ❖ Only the sample of 100 students have been taken from three faculties of I.P. P.G. College students in the present study.
- ❖ The present study is a survey of Social intelligence, only on the gender and locality arise.

Significance of the Study :

As we all know education plays a pivotal role in modern society. The aim of education is the all round development of a child all round means cognitive, effective and psychomotor development which will further effect the success of child. Our educational institute, therefore have a prime duty to being out the whole of a child. For this long with academic knowledge, social development is also necessary.

Many person consider that the Social intelligence has nothing to do with life of an individual. They seldom pay attention on it. This study will help the students to know about the importance of Social intelligence in their daily activities, which will help them of change their attitude towards their various activities in personal life.

This study is significant for the administrators as they can know about the Social intelligence on the adjustment of their students which can them to bring changes in the academic planning and transaction of curriculum.

This study will help the parents to know about the Social intelligence to their wards. Accordingly, they can they can change their views regarding with the interaction with society.

This study is also useful for the curriculum makers, because with the help of knowing about the Social intelligence , they can construct the curriculum according to the level of student's interest and intelligence.

This study is also helpful and very much truitful in respect to teachers, because Social intelligence is directly linked to the interaction with society and this quality or trait of Social intelligence will ultimately lead to the academic enhancement and also in the betterment of teacher-student interaction.

Similarly, the Social intelligence also plays a vital role in the administration of a school. As we all know that school is a form of mini society, where all the groups. classes and sects of a society moves and

interact to each other. In this situation Social intelligence is also useful in the respect of a school.

Therefore in the light of all the above points, it is significant to study the Social intelligence.

Review of Related Literature :

Wechsler (1939,1958) gave scant attention to the concept, Wechsler did acknowledge that the Picture Arrangement subtest of the WAIS might serve as a measure of social intelligence because it assesses the individual ability to comprehend social situation Rapport, Gill and Shaper 1968 Campbell and McCord 1996 also give their opinion on this topic In his view however Social intelligence is just general intelligence applied to "social situation" This dismissal is reported in Mataruzzo's (1972 p.209) fifth addition of Wechsler's monograph in which "dropped out as an index term.

Guilford's (1967) more differentiated system social intelligence is represented as the 30 (5 operations x 6 products) abilities lying in the domain of behavioral operation. In contrast to its extensive work on semantic and figural content, Guilford's group addressed issues of behavioral content only very late in their program of research. Nevertheless of the 30 facets of social intelligence predicted by the structure of intellect mode actual tests were devised for six cognitive abilities and six divergent production abilities.

O'Sullivan (1965) defined the category of behavioral cognition as representing the "ability to judge people" with respect to "feeling motives thoughts, intentions, attitudes or other psychological dispositions which might affect an individual's social behavior" (O'Sullivan p.4). They made it clear that one's ability to judge individual people was not the same as his or her comprehension of people in general or "stereotypic understanding" and bore no a prior relation to one's ability to understand oneself. Apparently these two aspects of social cognition lie standard structure of intellect model.

Keating (1978) measured social intelligence with a battery of including Rest's (1975) defining issues Test derived from Kohlberg's (1963) theory of moral development Chapin's (1942) social insight test, which asks the subject to resolve various social dilemmas Gough's (1966). Social Maturity Index a self report scale derived from the

California Psychological inventory measuring effective social function. Applying a multitrait-multimethod analysis, Keating found no evidence that social intelligence so defined was discriminable from academic intelligence. Thus the average correlation between tests within each domain was actually lower than the corresponding average across these factors consisted of a mix of the two types of intelligence test. Finally, Keating found that the three measures of abstract intelligence. However, it should intelligence are highly verbal in nature, so some contamination by abstract verbal and reasoning ability might be expected.

An exception to the general rule that social intelligence plays little role in scientific theories of social intelligence is the theory of multiple intelligence proposed by Gardner (1993,1993.) Unlike Spearman (1927) and other advocates of general intelligence (e.g. Jensen,1998) Gardner has proposed that intelligence is not a unitary cognitive ability, but that there are seven (and perhaps more) quite different kinds of intelligence, each hypothetically dissociable from the others, and each hypothetically associated with a different brain system. White most of these proposed intelligences (linguistics, logical-mathematical, spatial, musical and bodily kinesthetic) are "cognitive" abilities somewhat reminiscent of Thurston's primary mental abilities, two are explicitly personal and social in nature. Gardner defines intrapersonal intelligence as the person's ability to gain access to his own internal emotional life, and interpersonal intelligence as the individual's ability to notice and make distinction among other individuals.

Cantor and Kihlstrom (1987) social intelligence is specifically geared to solving the problems of social life, and in particular managing the life tasks, current concerns (Klinger 1977) or personal projects (Litte,1989) which the person selects for him or herself, or which other people impose on him or her from outside. Put another way, one's social intelligence cannot be evaluated in the abstract, but only with respect to the domains and contexts in which it is exhibited and the tasks it is designed to serve and even in this case, "adequacy" cannot be judged from the view point of the external observer, but rather from the point of view of the subject whose life tasks are in play.

Methodology :

In order to make the research successful, the researcher should select the appropriate procedure. This research is survey type since the survey research is an organized attempt to analysis, interpret and report the present status of social institution group or area. According to Morse H.N. "The survey is a method of analysis in scientific and orderly forms for defied purpose of given social situation of problem or population". Actually the term survey is used for technique of investigation by a direct observation of a present phenomenon for population by applying personal contact and interviews when an adequate information about a certain problem is not available in records, files and other sources.

In present study researcher surveyed various departments of the college and collected data through personal contact with sample, students. The researcher collected the information about their social intelligence by giving them social intelligence scale SIS and later on analyzed the result statistically.

Population :

All the students studying in various departments in I.P. P.G. College, Bulandshahr, U.P. are the population for the present study.

Sample and the sampling technique :

The primary purpose of a research is to discover the principles that have universal application but to study a whole population in order to assure at generalization would be next to impossible. The process to sampling makes it possible to draw valid inferences or generalization on the basis of careful observations of manipulation of variables, within a relatively small proportion of the population.

Without sampling it would not have possible to obtain valid results. Sample help to collect vital information more quickly. It helps to obtain more comprehensive data. But the main point which needs due consideration is adequateness and representativeness of a sample.

In order to obtain the objectives of the study, 100 students 50 boys and 50 girls of I.P. P.G. College were randomly selected. There students were selected from the three main faculties of college, running

professional courses. These are Faculty of Education, Faculty of Bio-Technology and Faculty of Business Management and Administration.

Tool :

The tool used for this study was Social Intelligence Scale (SIS) developed by Dr. Chadha and Usha Ganesan.

Statistical technique :

Mean (X) -

The formula for the mean is -

$$M = \Sigma X / N$$

Where,

M=Mean

Σ =Sum of

X=Scores in a distribution

N=Number of scores

Standard Deviation -

$$SD (\sigma) = \sqrt{X^2 / N - (\Sigma X / N)^2}$$

Where ,N=No of Scores

D=Deviation from mean

ΣX =Sum of the scores

ΣX^2 =Sum of the squares of the scores

T-test -

$$t = \frac{m - \bar{m}}{\sigma_d}$$

when $N > 30$

$$\sigma_D = \sqrt{S^2_1 / n_1 + S^2_2 / n_2}$$

when $N \leq 30$

$$\sigma_D = \sqrt{S^2_1 / n_1 - 1 + S^2_2 / n_2 - 1}$$

where,

S_1 and S_2 =standard deviation of first and second groups.

n_1 and n_2 = No. of sample scores .

σ_D = Standard error of the difference between means
of the two groups

Analysis and Interpretation of Data :

Phase-I : Comparison between Social Intelligence of Male and Female Students

Table-1
Mean scores of male and female students on Patience Dimension of SIS

Sex	N	M	S.D.	't'
Male	50	20.28	2.25	3.92**
Female	50	22.32	2.99	

*p = significant at 0.05 level, **p = significant at 0.01 level

The data shown in table-1 expresses that there is significant difference ($r=3.92$, $p=0.1$) between the male and female students in social intelligence on patience dimension of SIS.

The table shows that mean values of male and female students is 20.28 respectively. According to manual these data represent high social intelligence on patience dimension of SIS. But it is clear from the above table that the mean score of females is higher than that of males suggesting that females have good social intelligence as compared to males on patience dimension.

The reason being this findings may be that the females feel more responsibility than the males.

Table-2
Mean scores of male and female students on Co-operativeness Dimension of SIS

Sex	N	M	S.D.	't'
Male	50	26.76	2.89	0.12
Female	50	26.70	1.95	

The table-2 shows the data which reveals that there is no significant difference ($t=0.12$) between the male and female students in social intelligence on co-operativeness dimension of SIS.

Table-3

Mean scores of male and female students on Confidence Level Dimension of SIS

Sex	N	M	S.D.	't'
Male	50	21.30	1.84	0.67
Female	50	21.52	1.66	

The data in table-3 suggests that there is no significant difference ($t=0.67$) between the male and female students in on confidence level dimension of SIS.

The data in table above shows that the mean values of males and females is 21.30 and 21.52 respectively. According to manual these data represent high social intelligence on confidence level of SIS.

Table-4

Mean scores of male and female students on Sensitivity Dimension of SIS

Sex	N	M	S.D.	't'
Male	50	21.32	2.80	4.37**
Female	50	23.81	3.06	

The table - 4 shows the data which reveals that there is a significant difference ($t=4.37$, $p = 01$) between the male and female students in social intelligence on sensitivity dimension of SIS.

The data in table above shows that the mean values of males and females is 21.32 and 23.81 respectively. According to manual these data show males are low sensitive and females are average sensitive inferring average social intelligence of the female groups on this dimension and poor social intelligence of the male group on this dimension. Thus, on sensitivity dimension of social intelligence female students are better than the male students. The probable reason behind the better sensitivity among female students may be due to their basic personality characteristic of being emotional.

Table - 5

**Mean social intelligence scores of male and female students
 Total SIS.**

Sex	N	M	S.D.	't'
Male	50	106.68	8.83	0.34
Female	50	107.20	6.41	

When the mean scores of two categories of male and female students obtained on all the dimension of SIS were compared it was found that there is no significant difference ($t=0.34$) between the social intelligence of male and female students.

The table shows that the mean values of both male and female students is 106.68 and 107.20 respectively. According to manual, both values are slightly above the 50 percentile or above the average it represent both groups have average social intelligence.

**Phase-II : Comparison between social intelligence of Rural
 and Urban Students**

Table - 6

**Mean scores of rural and urban students on patience
 dimension of SIS**

Sex	N	M	S.D.	't'
Male	51	22.35	1.82	3.80**
Female	49	20.76	2.47	

The data shown in table - 6 expresses that there is a significant difference ($t=3.80$, $p=0.01$) between the social intelligence of rural and urban students on patience dimension of SIS.

The table shows that the mean value of rural and urban students is 22.35 and 20.76 respectively. According to manual, rural students mean value represent very high social intelligence on this dimension and urban students mean value show high social intelligence on this dimension. But comparatively the mean score of rural students

is higher than the urban students, it infers that rural students have more patience due to facing more problem from starting of their lives.

Table - 7

Mean scores of rural and urban students on co-operativeness dimension of SIS

Sex	N	M	S.D.	't'
Male	51	28.37	2.13	4.27**
Female	49	26.28	2.70	

Table - 7 shows the data that express that there is a significant difference ($t=4.27$, $p=0.01$) between the social intelligence of rural and urban students on co-operativeness dimension of SIS.

The table shows that the mean value of rural and urban students is 28.37 and 26.28 respectively. According to manual mean value of rural students represent above the high social intelligence on this dimension and urban students mean value represent average social intelligence on this dimension. That's mean rural students are more co-operative than the urban students. The reason behind the finding is probably rural's students belongs to combined family instead of nuclear family which is living trend in urban areas now a days. Generally, in combined family we see more co-operativeness among the family members which later on helps in the personality development and enhancement social intelligence of an individual.

Table-8

Mean scores of rural and urban students on confidence level dimension of SIS

Locality	N	M	S.D.	't'
Rural	51	20.56	1.64	4.23**
Urban	49	22.04	1.85	

The look on table-8 makes it evident that is significant difference ($t=4.23$, $p=0.01$) between the social intelligence of rural and urban students on confidence level dimension of SIS.

The data in table above that shows that mean values of rural and urban students is 20.56 and 22.04 respectively. According to manual mean value of rural students show high social intelligence on this dimension. Inferring good social intelligence of the both the groups on this dimension. The mean value of urban students is comparatively higher than the mean value of rural students implying that urban students possess better confidence level than rural students.

The reason probably may be that urban students have more opportunities to express their views and ideas at many fields in their academic area and personal life whereas the rural families do not have as much as possibility of expression of views in comparison to urban one.

Table - 9
Mean scores of rural and urban students on sensitivity dimension of SIS

Locality	N	M	S.D.	't'
Rural	51	21.78	2.30	0.94
Urban	49	21.30	2.81	

The data shown in table-9 expresses that there is no significance difference ($t= 0.94$) between the social intelligence of rural and urban students on sensitivity dimension of SIS.

The data in table above shows that the mean value of rural and urban students is 21.78 and 21.30 respectively. According to manual the mean value represent approximately above to average social intelligence on this dimension. It suggests that both the groups have average social intelligence on this dimension

Table – 10
Mean social intelligence scores of rural and urban students
Total SIS

Locality	N	M	S.D.	't'
Rural	51	108.50	5.99	2.43*
Urban	49	104.75	9.04	

The look on table-10 makes it evident that is significant difference ($t=2.43, p=0.05$) between mean scores of two categories of rural and urban students obtained on all the dimension of SIS.

The table shows that the mean value of rural and urban students is 108.50 and 104.75 respectively. According to manual mean value score represent above 50 percentile that means above average social intelligence and urban students score represent 5 percentile which mean average social intelligence. It suggests that both groups have average social intelligence. But it is clear from the above table that the mean score of rural students is higher than the urban students suggesting that rural students have good social intelligence as compared to urban students.

Normally, people think that the urban student have more social intelligence but the findings shows an another picture. In the rural shows the high social intelligence because as we know that our rural areas and their way of life and tradition and customs enhanced the social skills and ultimately, that leads to the social intelligence in respect to urban students because urban one has the modern way of life.

Phase-III : Comparison between social intelligence of three faculty

Table-11
Mean scores of students on patience dimension of SIS

Faculty	N	M	S.D.	Groups of comparison	't'
Faculty of Education (A)	50	22.81	1.86	A Vs B	5.02**
Faculty of Bio-Technology (B)	40	20.70	2.12	B Vs C	2.09*
Faculty of Computer Science (C)	10	22.79	2.99	C Vs A	0.02

The data shown in table-11 expresses that there is a significant difference ($t=5.02$, $p=0.01$) between the social intelligence of A and B groups on patience dimension of SIS.

There is a significant difference ($t=2.09$, $p=0.05$) between the social intelligence of B and C groups on patience dimension of SIS.

There is a significant difference (0.02) between the social intelligence of C and A groups on patience dimension of SIS.

The table shows that the mean value of A, B and C groups is 22.81, 20.70 and 22.79 respectively. According to manual A, B and C groups have very high social intelligence on this dimension and B group has high social intelligence on this dimension. It suggests that all these three groups have good social intelligence. But it is clear from the above table C group have better than A and B group have better than C.

The reason probably may be that A and C group both are belonging to humanistic subjects and both are interact directly to the society. But B group maximum spent time with the laboratory or machine. It may be the reason for bad performance on SIS at the patience dimension.

Table-12
Mean scores of students on Co-operativeness dimension of SIS

Faculty	N	M	S.D.	Groups of comparison	't'
Faculty of Education (A)	50	26.59	2.38	A Vs B	0.96
Faculty of Bio-Technology (B)	40	27.07	2.42	B Vs C	1.06
Faculty of Computer Science (C)	10	26.00	2.98	C Vs A	0.59

The perusal of table-12 reveals that there is no significant difference ($t=50.96$, $t=1.06$, $t=0.59$) between any of two groups in social intelligence on co-operativeness dimension of SIS.

The table shows that the mean value of A, B and C groups is 26.59, 27.07 and 26.00 respectively. According to manual mean value of

all groups above average social intelligence on the co-operativeness dimension. It implies that all the groups are good in co-operativeness.

Table - 13

Mean scores of students on confidence level dimension of SIS

Faculty	N	M	S.D.	Groups of comparison	't'
Faculty of Education (A)	50	21.43	1.70	A Vs B	0.25
Faculty of Bio-Technology (B)	40	21.51	1.73	B Vs C	0.87
Faculty of Computer Science (C)	10	20.90	2.08	C Vs A	0.76

The data presented in table-13 makes it evident that there is no significant difference ($t=0.25$, $t=0.87$, $t=0.76$) between any of two groups in social intelligence on confidence level dimension of SIS.

The table shows that the mean value of A,B and C groups is 21.43, 21.50 and 20.90 respectively. According to manual mean value of all groups show high social intelligence on the confidence level dimension. It infers that all the groups have high confidence level .

Table - 14

Mean scores of students on sensitivity dimension of SIS

Faculty	N	M	S.D.	Groups of comparison	't'
Faculty of Education (A)	50	21.08	2.64	A Vs B	0.01
Faculty of Bio-Technology (B)	40	21.90	2.59	B Vs C	2.93**
Faculty of Computer Science (C)	10	22.40	1.42	C Vs A	2.27*

The data shown in table-14 expresses that there is no significant difference ($t=0.01$) between the social intelligence of A and B groups on sensitivity dimension of SIS.

There is a significant difference ($t=2.93$, $p=0.01$) between the social intelligence of B and C groups on sensitivity dimension of SIS.

There is a significant difference (0.02) between the social intelligence of C and A groups on sensitivity dimension of SIS.

The table shows that the mean value of A, B and C groups is 21.08, 21.90 and 22.40 respectively. According to manual mean value of A groups represent average social intelligence this dimension and mean value of B and C groups show approximately high social intelligence on this dimension.

As we know that the course related to engineering field has the various topics of machines and logics which lead the development of sensitivity.

Similarly, the management group also has the course related to logical view point that is a plus point for sensitivity.

Table - 15

Mean social intelligence scores of students Total SIS

Faculty	N	M	S.D.	Groups of comparison	't'
Faculty of Education (A)	50	105.77	7.18	A Vs B	0.68
Faculty of Bio-Technology (B)	40	107.45	14.18	B Vs C	1.15
Faculty of Computer Science (C)	10	111.69	8.77	C Vs A	1.92

When the mean scores of three groups of Faculty of Education A, Faculty of Bio-Technology B, Faculty of Computer Science C, obtained on all dimension of SIS were compared it was found that there is no significant difference ($t=0.68$, $t=1.15$, $t=1.92$) between any two groups in social intelligence of overall dimensions.

The table shows that the mean value of A, B and C groups is 105.77, 107.45 and 111.69 respectively. According to manual mean value A and B groups represent approximately 50 percentile $p=50$ condition on social intelligence that means both group shows approximately 75 percentile ($p=75$) condition on social intelligence.

Conclusions :

Following are the main findings of the findings -

1. The overall social intelligence of college students of average. Sex wise analysis of data shows that male students are slightly above average in social intelligence females are above average. Locality wise analysis reveals that rural and urban students are above average in social intelligence. Faculty wise analysis of infers that the students of Faculty of Education are average in social intelligence. Faculty of Bio-Technology are above average while students of Faculty of Computer Science are good in social intelligence.
2. On patience dimension of social intelligence, males are above average level females are high level, and rural students are of high level urban students are of above average level, students of Faculty of Education and Faculty of Computer Science are of high level while students of Faculty of Bio-Technology are of average level in social intelligence.
3. On co-operativeness dimension of social intelligence male and female both have average level, rural students are of high level, urban students are of average level, Faculty of Education and Faculty of Computer Science students both are of average level while Faculty of Bio-Technology students are above average in social intelligence.
4. On confidence dimension of social intelligence male and females both have high level, rural students are of high level, urban students are of very high level, students of Faculty of Education, Faculty of Computer Science and Faculty of Bio-Technology are all of high level in social intelligence.
5. On sensitivity dimension of social intelligence males have average level, females are of very high level, rural students are of high urban students are of average level, students of Faculty of Education and Faculty of Bio-Technology are average level, while students of Faculty of Computer Science are high level in social intelligence.
6. On recognition of social environment dimension of social intelligence male and female both students have low level, rural and urban students are of low level also students of Faculty of Education and Faculty of Bio-Technology are of low level while

students of Faculty of Computer Science are of average level in social intelligence.

7. The first null hypothesis that there is no significant difference between the male and female students on various dimensions of social intelligence is partially accepted, partially rejected.

There is significant difference between the social intelligence of male and female students particularly on patience, sensitivity, tactfulness and sense of humour dimensions. Social intelligence of male students is better in tactfulness and sense of humour dimensions and of female students is better in patience and sensitivity dimension.

However, there is no significant difference between the social intelligence of male and female students co-operativeness, confidence level.

8. The second null hypothesis that there is no significant difference between rural and urban students on various dimensions of social intelligence is partially accepted, partially rejected.

There is significant difference between the social intelligence of rural and urban students particularly on patience, Social intelligence of rural students is better in patience, co-operativeness and tactfulness dimensions and of urban students is better in confidence level dimension.

However, there is no significant difference between the social intelligence of rural and urban students on sensitivity recognition of social environment.

9. The third null hypothesis that there is no significant difference between student of three faculties is Faculty of Education are average in social intelligence, Faculty of Bio-Technology and Faculty of Computer Science on social intelligence is partially accepted, partially rejected.

- There is a significant difference between the social intelligence of Faculty of Education Allied Science are average in social intelligence. Faculty of Bio-Technology students particularly patience and tactfulness on these dimension. Social intelligence of Faculty of Education are average in social intelligence is better in

patience and Faculty of Bio-Technology is better in tactfulness dimension.

However, there is no significant difference between the social intelligence of Faculty of Education are average in social intelligence and Faculty of Bio-Technology students particularly of social environment sense of humour and memory dimensions.

- There is significant difference between the social intelligence of Faculty of Bio-Technology and Faculty of Computer Science particularly patience, sensitivity recognition of social environment and memory on these dimension. Social intelligence of Faculty of Computer Science is better than Faculty of Bio-Technology

However, there is no significant difference between the social intelligence of Faculty of Bio-Technology Faculty of Education are average in social intelligence particularly co-operativeness, confidence dimension.

- There s significant difference between the social intelligence of Faculty of Education students and Faculty of Computer Science students particularly sensitivity, recognition of social environment, tactfulness and memory on social environment, tactfulness and memory on these dimensions. Social intelligence of Faculty of Computer Science is better than Faculty of Education are average in social intelligence in above dimensions.

However, there is no significant difference between the social intelligence of Faculty of Education Faculty of Computer Science students particularly patience, co-operativeness, confidence level dimension.

Suggestions :

Since student is a part of society and nations's future. So it is responsibility of society to provide proper atmosphere for the students so that social intelligence could be developed. social intelligence is a factor for the development of all round personality of a student . So this study suggests to society and also to educational planner that they make a program or create a situation to develop social intelligence in students.

Suggestions for students - Graduate and other level students can improve their social intelligence by making strategies for the early stage of the professional life. They should take interest in various type of social activities and pay some weightage to it.

Suggestions for Parents - Parents are suggested to encourage their children/wards to participate in co-curricular activities like games, sports, dramas, debates, art, quiz etc. as good for improving social intelligence. It also suggests to the parents to promote their wards to participate in social activities and cultural activities which are necessary for social intelligence.

Suggestion for teachers - Social intelligence is a term of imitation. So it cannot be developed by self. It develops in the students by the help of teachers and other person who is the role model of the students. So teachers should suggest the students to take interest in social work and some other activities like debates speech and games. This study also suggest that teacher should motivate society and school.

Suggestions for administrators - This study suggests the administrators to make up or create appropriate environment for rising social intelligence. In this way students make up their mind for their present learning and training situations and future managements to give rise their productivity at work.

Suggestions for future research :

1. The present study is restricted to I.P P.G. College, Bulandshar only, further study can be spread on the wider population. It can be done on state level national level or international level.
2. The study is restricted to three professional courses, so the same project can be done for broad and different classifications or on different basis. For example-
 - Study for the people of different living classes Higher and lower income, employed and unemployed, etc.
 - Study for the people of different age groups.
 - Study for the people who are posted at higher responsible posts.
 - Study for the people of different cultural background.
 - Study for the married and unmarried peoples.

3. Present study have been done for only a sample of 100 students belonging to three faculties, which can be increase in further studies fir more accuracy.

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